

Studies in the Synthesis of Biphenyls

C. S. Kallianpur and J. R. Merchant

By application of the Ullmann reaction 2-methyl-4,5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl, 2,3'-dimethyl-4,5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl, and 2-acetoxymethyl-2'-dimethylamino-4,5-methylenedioxybiphenyl have been synthesised.

With a view to studying the scope of the Ullmann reaction, syntheses of 3'-ethyl-2'-dimethylamino-2-methyl-4,5-methylenedioxybiphenyl (I) and 2-acetoxymethyl-4,5-methylenedioxy-2'-dimethylaminobiphenyl (II) have been investigated. The former biphenyl derivative was isolated by the Emde degradation of lycorine (Taylor *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 929), whereas compound (II) was believed to be one of the degradation products obtained from the alkaloid tazettine by a Hofmann degradation (Weisner and Valenta, *ibid.*, 1956, R. 36).

Synthesis of the biphenyl derivative (I) by application of the Ullmann reaction between 2-iodo-4,5-methylenedioxytoluene (III) and 3-bromo-2-nitro-1-ethylbenzene (Elson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2741) failed to provide the desired biphenyl. Model compounds, *e.g.*, 2-methyl-4,5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl and 2,3'-dimethyl-4,5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl, could, however, be obtained by condensation of (III) with 2-nitro-1-bromobenzene and 3-bromo-2-nitrotoluene respectively under conditions of the Ullmann reaction.

The starting material for the preparation of compound (III) was the known 3,4-methylenedioxytoluene, which was iodinated in ethanolic solution in presence of yellow mercuric oxide to yield 2-iodo-4,5-methylenedioxytoluene. The position of iodine in (III) was established by oxidising it with potassium permanganate to 2-iodo-4,5-methylenedioxybenzoic acid. The latter compound was also synthesised by another route, starting with the known 4,5-methylenedioxy-2-nitrotoluene (Foulds and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 105, 1966), which on reduction and diazotisation gave 2-iodo-4,5-methylenedioxytoluene. The latter being an oil had to be oxidised to the corresponding benzoic acid for purposes of comparison.

For the synthesis of compound (II), 6-bromopiperonal (Parijs, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1930, 49, 27; *Chem. Abs.*, 1929, 23, 4204) was allowed to react with 2-bromo-1-nitrobenzene in presence of copper powder to form 2-formyl-4, 5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl. The latter was reduced with sodium borohydride, when 2-hydroxymethyl-4, 5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl (IV) resulted. On hydrogenation in presence of Raney nickel, 2'-amino-2-hydroxymethyl-4, 5-methylenedioxybiphenyl was obtained. Methylation of the latter and treatment with acetic anhydride afforded compound (II), m.p. 125-26°. In another experiment, (IV) was acetylated and the crude acetyl derivative was directly hydrogenated to afford 2-acetoxymethyl-2'-amino-4, 5-methylenedioxybiphenyl, isolated as an oil. This on methylation also gave (II), as indicated by mixed m.p.

EXPERIMENTAL

3, 4-Methylenedioxytoluene.—To a suspension of LiAlH_4 (3.4 g.) in dry ether (120 c.c.) was added dropwise with stirring a solution of piperonyl chloride (5 g.) (Decker and Koch, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 174) in dry ether (30 c.c.). After stirring for 3 hours and gentle refluxing of ether, the excess reducing agent was decomposed with cold 10% H_2SO_4 . On distillation of ether, an oil of b.p. 48-50°/2 mm was obtained; yield 2.5 g. (Ashkinazi and Rabinovitch, *J. Appl. Chem., U.S.S.R.*, 1937, 10, 131).

2-Iodo-4, 5-methylenedioxytoluene.—A solution of 4, 5-methylenedioxytoluene (18.4 g.) in ethanol (50 c.c.) was treated alternately in small lots, with stirring, with finely powdered iodine (30.4 g.) and yellow mercuric oxide (16.5 g.) in course of an hour. The solution was filtered and the residue was washed with hot ethanol. The concentrated filtrate was taken up in ether and washed successively with 20% sodium thiosulphate, 10% NaOH solution, and water. After drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate it distilled at 108-10°/2 mm as a yellow oil; yield 12.0 g. (Found: I, 48.8. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{O}_2\text{I}$ requires I, 48.5%). It was obtained through another way (*vide infra*).

2-Iodo-4, 5-methylenedioxybenzoic Acid.—The preceding compound (1.0 g.) was added to a mixture of potassium permanganate (5.0 g.) and magnesium sulphate (2.0 g.) in water (60 c.c.). The solution was refluxed for 12 hours and then a current of sulphur dioxide was passed into it, when a solid separated out. It was crystallised twice from dilute methanol in white needles, m.p. 38-39°. (Found: I, 43.8. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{I}$ requires I, 43.48%).

2-Amino-4, 5-methylenedioxytoluene.—4: 5-methylenedioxy-2-nitrotoluene (1.0 g.), dissolved in ethanol (25 c.c.), was hydrogenated in presence of Raney nickel for 4 hours. To the concentrated solution HCl (conc.) was added, when hydrochloride of 2-amino-4, 5-methylenedioxytoluene separated out. It was crystallised in fine white needles from methanol-ethyl acetate, m.p. 221-22°. (Found: N, 7.6. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$ requires N, 7.5%). The free amino compound was not very stable and after two crystallisations from methanol had m.p. 94-96°.

The amino-toluene was diazotised to 2-iodo-4: 5-methylenedioxytoluene in the following way: The hydrochloride of 2-amino-4, 5-methylenedioxytoluene (1.0 g.) in H_2SO_4 (conc., 1.6 c.c.) and crushed ice (8.5 g.) was treated below 0° with a solution of sodium nitrite (1.0 g.) in water (4.0 c.c.). The diazotised solution was then added to a solution of potassium iodide (1.0 g.) in water (2.0 c.c.), previously warmed to about 40°. The solution was extracted with ether, washed with a little HCl and water, and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Distillation of ether furnished 2-iodo-4, 5-methylenedioxytoluene as an oil. It was oxidised as before to 2-iodo-4, 5-methylenedioxybenzoic acid, confirmed by mixed m.p. with the acid obtained before.

2-Methyl-4, 5-methylenedioxy-2-nitrobiphenyl.—A mixture of 2-iodo-4, 5-methylenedioxy-toluene (2.2 g.) and 2-bromo-1-nitrotoluene (1.01 g.) (Ullmann, *Ber.*, 1896, 29B, 1880) was heated to 170° and copper powder (2.2 g.) was added in small lots with stirring during 10 minutes; the mixture was kept at 168-70° for 10 minutes and then its temperature was raised to 225-30° and maintained there for 50 minutes. The mixture after being cooled was extracted with hot ethanol (125 c.c.), charcoaled, and the solvent removed by distillation. The residue was crystallised from ligroin (b.p. 100-120°) and finally sublimed at 120-22°/2 mm to furnish triangular plates, m.p. 134-35°, yield 0.95 g. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 4.3. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 65.3; H, 4.28%).

3-Bromo-2-nitrotoluene was prepared by a method analogous to that described for the preparation of 3-chloro-2-nitrotoluene (Elson *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The structure of the bromo compound was confirmed by its oxidation to the known 3-bromo-2-nitrobenzoic acid (Holleman, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1901, 20, 215).

2, 3'-Dimethyl-4, 5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl was prepared from 2-iodo-4, 5-methylenedioxytoluene (1.98 g.) and 3-bromo-2-nitrotoluene (0.99 g.) with copper powder (2.2 g.) in the same way as described in the case of 2-methyl-4, 5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl (*vide supra*) at 168°. It was crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 127-28°, yield 0.63 g. (Found: C, 66.6; H, 4.9. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 66.4; H, 4.8%).

2-Formyl-4, 5-methylenedioxy-2-nitrobiphenyl.—To a mixture of 6-bromopiperonal (6.06 g.) and 2-bromo-1-nitrobenzene (3.08 g.) was added copper bronze (7.0 g.) with stirring in course of 10 minutes, keeping the temperature at 175-85°. The temperature of the reaction mixture was gradually raised to about 240-45° and maintained there for 1 hour. The hard mass was extracted with a mixture of ethanol-acetone (2: 1). The solution was charcoaled and the solvent distilled. The pasty mass obtained was boiled with rectified spirit (30 c.c.). The solid separating was filtered and sublimed at 200-10°/3 mm, and finally crystallised from ethyl acetate in brownish plates, m.p. 227-28°, yield 7.50 mg. (Found: C, 62.3; H, 3.4. $C_{14}H_9O_5N$ requires C, 61.98; H, 3.32%).

2-Hydroxymethyl-4, 5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl.—To the preceding compound (0.5 g.) in methanol (15 c.c.) was added sodium borohydride (0.25 g.); the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hours. On cooling, acetic acid (2 c.c.) was added to decompose the excess of sodium borohydride. The concentrated solution was diluted with water, when a brown solid separated out. It was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 168-69°, yield 0.35 mg. (Found: N, 5.3. $C_{14}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 5.0%).

2-Amino-2-hydroxymethyl-4, 5-methylenedioxybiphenyl.—A suspension of the above 2'-nitrobiphenyl derivative (100 mg.) in ethanol (30 c.c.) was reduced with Raney nickel (10 c.c. suspension) for 4 hours. The filtered solution was concentrated and then diluted with water to obtain the amino compound. It was crystallised from dilute methanol, m.p. 151-52°. (Found: C, 68.8; H, 5.8; N, 6.1. $C_{14}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 69.1; H, 5.4; N, 5.8%).

The same compound was also obtained by hydrogenation of 2-formyl-4, 5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl in presence of Raney nickel.

2-Acetoxyethyl-2'-dimethylamino-4, 5-methylenedioxybiphenyl.—To the above aminobiphenyl (188 mg.) were added alternately and with stirring dimethyl sulphate (228 mg.) and 30% NaOH solution (0.25 c.c.) during 5 minutes. After further addition of the alkali (0.1 c.c.) the mixture was extracted with ether; the ether solution was washed with 2-3 c.c. portions of water. After drying and distilling ether, a pasty mass was obtained. It was heated with acetic anhydride (1.5 c.c.) on a water bath for 5 minutes and the latter was removed under vacuum. The residue

was taken up in ether and the ether solution extracted with 2*N*-HCl (15 c.c.). The acid layer was separated and neutralised with 2*N*-NaOH to pH 8.0. The alkaline solution was extracted with ether and the ether solution was washed with water. Distillation of the ether gave a pale yellow solid. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°), m.p. 125-26°. (Found: C, 68.6; H, 6.0; N, 4.8. C₁₈H₁₉O₄N requires C, 68.99; H, 6.4; N, 4.47%).

In another experiment 2-hydroxymethyl-4, 5-methylenedioxy-2'-nitrobiphenyl was acetylated with acetic anhydride (0.7 c.c.) (containing a drop of pyridine) at 100° for 30 minutes. The resulting mixture was poured into water, when a brownish semi-solid was obtained. It did not solidify even after keeping in a refrigerator for 3 days. It was extracted with ether and the ether solution was washed successively with bicarbonate, HCl, and water. Removal of the solvent afforded 80 mg. of a dark oil. It was directly hydrogenated in ethanolic solution in presence of Raney nickel, when a brownish oil resulted. It was methylated, as described above, when a compound melting at 125-26° and identical with 2-acetoxymethyl-2'-dimethylamino-4, 5-methylenedioxybiphenyl was obtained (mixed m.p.).

INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BOMBAY-1.

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